

ORIGINAL RESEARCH**C⁺⁺ Software Program for Downdraft Gasifier Design and Development**

Aly Radwan

¹National Research Center, Egypt**Correspondence**

Aly Radwan

Corresponding Author:

radwannrc@hotmail.com

Received: 15 January, 2022

Accepted: 27 February, 2022

Published: 03 March, 2022

Abstract

Biomass gasification is an important process of converting biomass into a gaseous fuel through a sequence processes of thermochemical reactions. Prototype of down draft gasifier was designed to generate synthesis gas for house hold applications. C⁺⁺ Software Program for the design and development of downdraft gasification system was done.

Keywords: Downdraft gasifier; Biomass; Synthesis gas; Software calculation

This is an open-access article published by the [Journal of Technology Innovations and Energy](#), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited

1.Introduction

Downdraft gasifiers reactors are the most suitable for rural areas using both small and medium sizes. The system can serve both the household and agriculture applications. The performance of gasification processes in a downdraft gasifier is affected by different factors including residence time, type of reactors, properties of the biomass feed, air to steam ratio and the addition of catalyst. These parameters are affecting on the performance of the gasifier.

The gas produced from gasification processes will be used for different application in rural areas such as drying, domestic cooking, irrigation pump and small scale industrial process. Downdraft gasifier has been applied in China for domestic cooking. Downdraft gasifier of 6-7 kw was designed and constructed in India. Many gasifiers system has been applied in India for heating and small industrial processes (1-8).

The present article deals with software program C⁺⁺ for design and development of downdraft gasifier .

Processes in downdraft gasifier

In the downdraft gasifier both biomass and air move in the downward direction in the lower part of the gasifier system. Down draft consists from four zones. The zones of gasification process such as drying, pyrolysis, oxidation and reduction is shown in Fig. 1.

The fed biomass is dried in the top of gasifier. The dried biomass moves downward to the upper-middle zone, enabling the pyrolysis and the tar conversion reactions to occur.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of downdraft gasifier

The unconverted tars and gases then evolve toward the oxidation zone, where the combustion takes place at higher temperature of 1000-1400 °C.

The chemical species formed finally move through a reduction zone where the H₂ and CO contents are enriched.

The product gas contains a low amount of particulates and tars (~ 1 g/Nm³) because most of the tars are combusted in the oxidation zone.

The downdraft gasifier is particularly well adapted when a clean syngas gas with a low content of tar and particulates is required.

Advantages & Disadvantages of Downdraft gasifier**Advantages**

Downdraft gasifier is very attractive for biomass gasification due to